

A SIMPLE MODEL FOR THE ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES WITH AND WITHOUT DELAMINATION

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SUMMARY: An approximate analytical elasticity solution for composite laminates undergoing a 3-D state of strain dependent on two coordinates is presented. The presence of delamination is accounted for. Simple and accurate approximations for interlaminar stresses and stiffness parameters are obtained for laminates subjected to axial extension and torsion. The model predictions are compared with existing analytical and numerical results.

KEYWORDS: elasticity, laminated composites, delamination, interlaminar stresses.

INTRODUCTION

Analysis of practical laminated composite structures often requires 3-D elasticity modeling. Since analytical solutions are available for few boundary value problems, numerical modeling is generally the only option. In some cases, the cost of large numerical simulations results in a need for developing approximate analytical elasticity solutions. One example is the design of laminated composite flexbeams in helicopter rotor systems. These symmetric laminates with a thick rectangular cross section entail a large number of candidate stacking sequences. Interlaminar stresses must be accurately determined to gain an understanding of the influence of the primary design variables such as ply orientation and stacking sequence on failure under tension, torsion and bending loading.

Distribution of the interlaminar stresses in the flexbeams is needed for selecting candidate configurations at the preliminary design stage. To this end, a cross sectional finite element stress analysis was applied by Sen and Fish [1, 2] to determine the stresses in glass-epoxy thirty-two-ply flexbeam laminates under torsion and combined tension-torsion loads. The largest mesh in the finite element analysis consisted of 7,144 elements with 21,945 degrees of freedom. The cost associated with the finite element modeling makes it highly inefficient for analyzing every candidate lay-up at the preliminary design stage. On the other hand, existing engineering laminated plate or beam theories, which would allow for a closed-form solution, are based on assumptions restricting the strain or stress state and, therefore, are not appropriate for a reliable prediction of all stress components.

The interlaminar stresses in symmetric laminates were first evaluated by Pipes and Pagano [3] for the case of uniform axial extension by applying a finite difference technique to solve the Navier equations of elasticity for off-axis plies. A number of finite element models were subsequently developed. Brief reviews are provided in Refs. [1] and [4]. Wang and Choi [4, 5] assumed the form of the stress functions in order to analytically solve the compatibility equations for two adjacent off-axis plies. A singular stress field at the free edge was obtained. While this solution provides a rigorous prediction of the free-edge interlaminar stresses, its mathematical complexity makes it unsuitable for practical multi-layer laminates. Other existing analytical approaches are based on *ad hoc* assumptions regarding the stress or strain fields in addition to the classical 2-D formulation of the 3-D strain state.

An iterative method for one-term approximate solution of partial differential equations was developed by Makeev [6]. The method was applied to several boundary value problems and its predictions were in a good agreement with exact solutions. The method was also used for predicting interlaminar stresses in symmetric laminates under axial extension and torsion in Ref. [7]. One- and two-term approximations for the stress functions were obtained. A close agreement was established with the numerical results of Pipes and Pagano [3], and Sen and Fish [2], and the analytical predictions of Wang and Choi [5]. The method is simple and, therefore, ideally suited for parametric design studies where a large number of candidate configurations need to be evaluated quickly and economically.

In this work, the approximate elasticity model [6] for laminated composites in a 3-D state of strain dependent on 2 coordinates [8] is presented. The presence of delaminations, a primary damage mode in laminated composites, is accounted for. Results for interlaminar stresses and stiffness parameters are compared with existing model predictions for laminates subjected to axial extension and torsion.

ANALYSIS

Elasticity Equations

Consider a laminated beam with rectangular cross section, subjected to four constant strain measures: the axial strain ε_0 , bending curvatures κ_1 and κ_2 , and twist rate θ . The laminate consists of plies with different material properties and the presence of delaminations or transverse cracks is taken into account. Accordingly, the cross section is divided into rectangular sublaminates, as shown in Fig. 1, with an independent set of the field variables in each sublaminate. A strain state independent of the longitudinal direction results in the following engineering strain-displacement relations [8]

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{xx} &= U_{,x} & \varepsilon_{yy} &= V_{,y} & \varepsilon_{zz} &= \varepsilon_0 + \kappa_1 x + \kappa_2 y \\ \gamma_{yz} &= \theta x + W_{,y} & \gamma_{xz} &= -\theta y + W_{,x} & \gamma_{xy} &= U_{,y} + V_{,x} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where U , V and W are functions of x and y . Subscript commas denote partial derivatives. The following compatibility equations can be obtained from eqns (1)

$$\varepsilon_{xx,yy} + \varepsilon_{yy,xx} - \gamma_{xy,xy} = 0 \quad \gamma_{xz,y} - \gamma_{yz,x} = -2\theta \quad (2)$$

An off-axis ply is modeled as a homogeneous medium with 13 non-zero elastic constants, 9 of which are independent [3]. The general constitutive relations [8] can be simplified to

$$\sigma^{zz} = \frac{1}{\alpha_{33}} \left(\varepsilon_{zz} - \alpha_{13} \sigma^{xx} - \alpha_{23} \sigma^{yy} - \alpha_{35} \sigma^{xz} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_{11} & \beta_{12} & \beta_{15} \\ \beta_{12} & \beta_{22} & \beta_{25} \\ \beta_{15} & \beta_{25} & \beta_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma^{xx} \\ \sigma^{yy} \\ \sigma^{xz} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_{13} \\ \alpha_{23} \\ \alpha_{35} \end{Bmatrix} \frac{\varepsilon_{zz}}{\alpha_{33}}, \quad \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_{44} & \beta_{46} \\ \beta_{46} & \beta_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma^{yz} \\ \sigma^{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1. Beam geometry

The stress functions identically satisfying the equilibrium equations are defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma^{xx} &= F_{,yy} & \sigma^{yy} &= F_{,xx} & \sigma^{xy} &= -F_{,xy} \\ \sigma^{xz} &= \Psi_{,y} & \sigma^{yz} &= -\Psi_{,x} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Substitute eqns (5) and (4) into the compatibility equations (2) to obtain

$$\beta_{22} F_{,xxxx} + (2\beta_{12} + \beta_{66}) F_{,xxyy} + \beta_{11} F_{,yyyy} + (\beta_{25} + \beta_{46}) \Psi_{,xxy} + \beta_{15} \Psi_{,yyy} = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$(\beta_{25} + \beta_{46}) F_{,xxy} + \beta_{15} F_{,yyy} + \beta_{44} \Psi_{,xx} + \beta_{55} \Psi_{,yy} = -2\theta \quad (7)$$

The boundary conditions at the traction free vertical edges, $x = \pm b$, and the transverse crack surfaces are

$$F = F_{,x} = \Psi = 0 \quad (8)$$

The conditions at the traction free horizontal edges, $y = \pm h$, and the delamination surfaces are

$$F = F_{,y} = \Psi = 0 \quad (9)$$

Due to the continuity of the interlaminar stresses and the displacements, the following expressions are continuous at the undamaged vertical sublaminar interfaces

$$\begin{aligned} &F, F_{,x}, \Psi, \\ &\beta_{12} F_{,yy} + \beta_{22} F_{,xx} + \beta_{25} \Psi_{,y} + \frac{\alpha_{23}}{\alpha_{33}} (\varepsilon_0 + \kappa_1 x + \kappa_2 y), \\ &(\beta_{12} + \beta_{66}) F_{,xxy} + \beta_{22} F_{,xxx} + (\beta_{25} + \beta_{46}) \Psi_{,xy} + \frac{\alpha_{23}}{\alpha_{33}} \kappa_1, \\ &\beta_{44} \Psi_{,x} + \beta_{46} F_{,xy} - \theta x \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

and the following quantities are continuous at the undamaged horizontal interfaces

$$\begin{aligned}
& F , F_{,y} , \Psi , \\
& \beta_{11}F_{,yy} + \beta_{12}F_{,xx} + \beta_{15}\Psi_{,y} + \frac{\alpha_{13}}{\alpha_{33}}(\varepsilon_0 + \kappa_1x + \kappa_2y) , \\
& \beta_{11}F_{,yyy} + (\beta_{12} + \beta_{66})F_{,xxy} + \beta_{15}\Psi_{,yy} + \beta_{46}\Psi_{,xx} + \frac{\alpha_{13}}{\alpha_{33}}\kappa_2 , \\
& \beta_{15}F_{,yy} + \beta_{25}F_{,xx} + \beta_{55}\Psi_{,y} + \frac{\alpha_{35}}{\alpha_{33}}(\varepsilon_0 + \kappa_1x + \kappa_2y) + \theta y
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Approximate Solution

Construct the following weak form of eqns (6) and (7)

$$\int_{y_1}^{y_2} dy \int_{x_1}^{x_2} [\beta_{22}F_{,xxx} + (2\beta_{12} + \beta_{66})F_{,xxy} + \beta_{11}F_{,yyy} + (\beta_{25} + \beta_{46})\Psi_{,xxy} + \beta_{15}\Psi_{,yyy}] \delta F dx = 0 \tag{12}$$

$$\int_{y_1}^{y_2} dy \int_{x_1}^{x_2} [(\beta_{25} + \beta_{46})F_{,xxy} + \beta_{15}F_{,yyy} + \beta_{44}\Psi_{,xx} + \beta_{55}\Psi_{,yy} + 2\theta] \delta \Psi dx = 0 \tag{13}$$

where y_1 and y_2 denote the horizontal, and x_1 and x_2 denote the vertical boundaries of the associated sublaminates (Fig. 1).

Consistent with eqns (12) and (13), obtain a weak form of the continuity conditions (10) and (11). If the complementary virtual work of the surface tractions at the sublaminates interface is considered, the following expressions are continuous at the undamaged vertical sublaminates interfaces

$$\int_{y_1}^{y_2} U \delta \sigma^{xx} dy , \quad \int_{y_1}^{y_2} V \delta \sigma^{xy} dy , \quad \int_{y_1}^{y_2} W \delta \sigma^{xz} dy \tag{14}$$

and the following expressions are continuous at the undamaged horizontal interfaces

$$\int_{x_1}^{x_2} U \delta \sigma^{xy} dx , \quad \int_{x_1}^{x_2} V \delta \sigma^{yy} dx , \quad \int_{x_1}^{x_2} W \delta \sigma^{yz} dx \tag{15}$$

Substitute eqns (5) into eqns (14) and (15), integrate by parts, and use eqns (1) and (4) to obtain the following weak form of the continuity conditions (10) and (11)

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \left[\beta_{12}F_{,yy} + \beta_{22}F_{,xx} + \beta_{25}\Psi_{,y} + \frac{\alpha_{23}}{\alpha_{33}}(\varepsilon_0 + \kappa_1x + \kappa_2y) \right] \delta F_{,x} dy , \\
& \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \left[(\beta_{12} + \beta_{66})F_{,xxy} + \beta_{22}F_{,xxx} + (\beta_{25} + \beta_{46})\Psi_{,xxy} + \frac{\alpha_{23}}{\alpha_{33}}\kappa_1 \right] \delta F dy , \\
& \int_{y_1}^{y_2} [\beta_{46}F_{,xy} + \beta_{44}\Psi_{,x} - \theta x] \delta \Psi dy
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \left[\beta_{11} F_{,yy} + \beta_{12} F_{,xx} + \beta_{15} \Psi_{,y} + \frac{\alpha_{13}}{\alpha_{33}} (\varepsilon_0 + \kappa_1 x + \kappa_2 y) \right] \delta F_{,y} dx , \\
& \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \left[\beta_{11} F_{,yyy} + (\beta_{12} + \beta_{66}) F_{,xxy} + \beta_{15} \Psi_{,yy} + \beta_{46} \Psi_{,xx} + \frac{\alpha_{13}}{\alpha_{33}} \kappa_2 \right] \delta F dx , \quad (17) \\
& \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \left[\beta_{15} F_{,yy} + \beta_{25} F_{,xx} + \beta_{55} \Psi_{,y} + \frac{\alpha_{35}}{\alpha_{33}} (\varepsilon_0 + \kappa_1 x + \kappa_2 y) + \theta y \right] \delta \Psi dx
\end{aligned}$$

The traction free boundary conditions (8) and (9) do not change.

Select the following first approximation for the stress functions

$$F^{(1)} = \sum_{i=1}^N f_{xi}^{(1)}(x) f_{yi}^{(1)}(y), \quad \Psi^{(1)} = \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_{xi}^{(1)}(x) \psi_{yi}^{(1)}(y) \quad (18)$$

where $f_{xi}^{(1)}(x)$ and $\psi_{xi}^{(1)}(x)$ are known functions satisfying the boundary conditions. Substitute expressions (18) into eqns (12) and (13), and integrate through x to obtain a system of ordinary differential equations for $f_{yi}^{(1)}(y)$ and $\psi_{yi}^{(1)}(y)$. The closed-form solution of this system is straightforward. Substitute eqns (18) into eqns (9) and (17) to obtain $6NM$ linear algebraic equations (N is the number of terms in approximations (18) and M is the number of sublaminates) for the unknown constants in the solution. Solving this system completes the first approximation which is equivalent to the method of approximate solution of partial differential equations developed by Kantorovich [9]. In order to make the solution of such systems as one considered in this work practically meaningful, the approximations have to have no more than one or two terms. However, these approximations are not accurate in general [6, 7]. The following simple iteration procedure allows for a significant improvement in accuracy without increasing the number of terms in the solution.

The second and higher approximations for the stress functions have the same form as the first approximation (18) with the same number of terms N in the series. The second approximation uses the functions $f_{yi}^{(1)}(y)$ and $\psi_{yi}^{(1)}(y)$ obtained from the first iteration

$$F^{(2)} = \sum_{i=1}^N f_{xi}^{(2)}(x) f_{yi}^{(1)}(y), \quad \Psi^{(2)} = \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_{xi}^{(2)}(x) \psi_{yi}^{(1)}(y) \quad (19)$$

Substitute expressions (19) into eqns (12), (13), (8) and (16), and integrate through y to formulate the boundary value problem for $f_{xi}^{(2)}(x)$ and $\psi_{xi}^{(2)}(x)$. The third approximation uses the x -dependent functions from the second iteration and the solution procedure is identical to the first iteration.

If both horizontal or both vertical boundaries of a sublaminate are traction free, the weak forms (12) and (13) together with the free edge boundary conditions will result in a trivial solution at the first or the second iterations, respectively, for the special cases of axial extension or bending. In such cases, the following weak forms of eqns (6) and (7), obtained from the principle of complementary virtual work, may be used

Odd iterations:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{y_1}^{y_2} dy \int_{x_1}^{x_2} [(\beta_{11} F_{,yyyy} + \beta_{12} F_{,xxyy} + \beta_{15} \Psi_{,yyy}) \delta F_{,yy} \\
& + \left(\beta_{12} F_{,yy} + \beta_{22} F_{,xx} + \beta_{25} \Psi_{,y} + \frac{\alpha_{23}}{\alpha_{33}} [\varepsilon_0 + \kappa_1 x + \kappa_2 y] \right) \delta F_{,xx} - (\beta_{46} \Psi_{,xy} + \beta_{66} F_{,xyy}) \delta F_{,x}] dx = 0
\end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

$$\int_{y_1}^{y_2} dy \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \left[\beta_{15} F_{,yyy} + \beta_{25} F_{,xxy} + \beta_{55} \Psi_{,yy} + \frac{\alpha_{35}}{\alpha_{33}} \kappa_2 \right] \delta \Psi_{,y} - (\beta_{44} \Psi_{,x} + \beta_{46} F_{,xy}) \delta \Psi_{,x} dy = 0 \quad (21)$$

Even iterations:

$$\int_{x_1}^{x_2} dx \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \left[\beta_{11} F_{,yy} + \beta_{12} F_{,xx} + \beta_{15} \Psi_{,y} + \frac{\alpha_{13}}{\alpha_{33}} [\varepsilon_0 + \kappa_1 x + \kappa_2 y] \right] \delta F_{,y} + (\beta_{12} F_{,xyy} + \beta_{22} F_{,xxx} + \beta_{25} \Psi_{,xxy}) \delta F - (\beta_{46} \Psi_{,xx} + \beta_{66} F_{,xxy}) \delta F_{,y} dy = 0 \quad (22)$$

$$\int_{x_1}^{x_2} dx \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \left[\beta_{15} F_{,yy} + \beta_{25} F_{,xx} + \beta_{55} \Psi_{,y} + \frac{\alpha_{35}}{\alpha_{33}} [\varepsilon_0 + \kappa_1 x + \kappa_2 y] \right] \delta \Psi_{,y} - (\beta_{44} \Psi_{,xx} + \beta_{46} F_{,xxy}) \delta \Psi dy = 0 \quad (23)$$

This iterative procedure allows for simple and accurate approximations for stresses. In Ref. [7], one- and two-term approximate solutions were compared with existing results for stresses in undamaged laminates under axial extension and torsion. One-term approximations provided the correct trend information and two-term approximations predicted an accurate stress state. Two-three iterations were sufficient for an accurate modeling. Predictions of interlaminar stresses and stiffness parameters for laminates subjected to axial extension and torsion are presented in the following section.

RESULTS

Axial Extension

For symmetric laminates subjected to axial extension, only a quarter of the laminate needs to be considered due to symmetry. The boundary conditions at the symmetry axes are defined in Ref. [3] as follows

$$x = 0, \quad W = V_{,x} = U = 0 \quad (24)$$

$$y = 0, \quad W_{,y} = V = U_{,y} = 0 \quad (25)$$

According to eqns (1), (4) and (5), expressions (24) and (25) result in the following conditions for the stress functions

$$x = 0, \quad F_{,x} = F_{,xxx} = \Psi_{,x} = 0 \quad (26)$$

$$y = 0, \quad F_{,y} = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} (\beta_{11} F_{,yyy} + \beta_{15} \Psi_{,yy}) \delta F = \Psi = 0 \quad (27)$$

According to eqns (26), f_{xi} and ψ_{xi} are even functions since their solution consists of combinations of trigonometric and exponential functions.

First, the approximate analytical solution is compared with the results of Pipes and Pagano [3], and Wang and Choi [5] for stresses in undamaged $[45/-45]_s$ graphite-epoxy laminates.

The thickness-to-width ratio is 0.25, and the material properties are

$$\begin{aligned} E_{33} &= 137.9 \text{ GPa (20.0 Msi)}, \quad E_{11} = E_{22} = 14.48 \text{ GPa (2.1 Msi)}, \\ G_{13} &= G_{23} = G_{12} = 5.86 \text{ GPa (0.85 Msi)}, \\ \nu_{31} &= \nu_{32} = \nu_{12} = 0.21 \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

The following x -dependent functions, satisfying the free-edge boundary conditions, are selected as the first approximation

$$f_{xi}^{(1)} = \cos \xi_i \frac{x}{b} - \frac{\cos \xi_i}{\cosh \xi_i} \cosh \xi_i \frac{x}{b}, \quad \psi_{xi}^{(1)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{hb}} \left(1 - \frac{\cosh \xi_i \frac{x}{b}}{\cosh \xi_i} \right), \quad (29)$$

$$\cos \xi_i \sinh \xi_i + \sin \xi_i \cosh \xi_i = 0$$

The distribution of the interlaminar shear stress σ_{yz} at the free edge $x=b$ is shown in Fig. 2 where the third iterations for one-, two- and three-term approximations are compared with the previously published results [3, 5]. While one-term approximation gives an accurate estimate at $x = 0.89b$, two- and three-term approximations are accurate at both $x = 0.89b$ and b . The largest order of the systems of linear algebraic equations for one-, two- and three-term approximations is 12, 24 and 36, respectively.

Next, the influence of damage, in the form of four symmetrically placed edge delaminations at the 45/-45 ply interfaces, on the axial stiffness is considered. Accordingly, a quarter of the cross section is divided into four sublaminates. The results of the second iteration for the undamaged laminate are used as the first approximation for the damaged case. One-term approximation predictions are compared with finite element results. The finite element predictions were generated by using the VABS (Variational Asymptotical Beam Simulation) code, which performs a cross sectional finite element analysis. This analysis, developed by Cesnik and Hodges [10], is based on the variational-asymptotical method [11] that is used to dimensionally reduce a 3-D elasticity problem for a beam of arbitrary geometry and material properties. The axial stiffness

$$EA = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \iint_{0 \leq x \leq b, 0 \leq y \leq h} \sigma^{zz} dx dy \quad (30)$$

normalized by the axial stiffness of the undamaged laminate is plotted in Fig. 3 as a function of the delamination length. The largest mesh in the finite element cross section model consisted of 640 elements with 1401 degrees of freedom. One system of linear algebraic equations of order 12 and two systems of order 6 had to be solved at the first and the third iterations. The second iteration resulted in 2 systems of 9 linear algebraic equations. The analytical and finite element predictions are within 1% relative difference.

Fig. 2. Comparison of interlaminar shear stress predictions at the free edge for axial extension of [45/-45]_s laminate

Fig. 3. Axial stiffness change due to delamination growth in [45/-45]_s laminate

Torsion

Predictions of the interlaminar shear stress σ_{yz} at the free edge are compared with the finite element results of Sen and Fish [2] for the torsion of a 32-ply $[0_{12}/\pm 30_2]_s$ S2/F584 glass-epoxy undamaged flexbeam laminate configuration. The width of the laminate is 38 mm, the thickness is 7.296 mm, and the material properties are

$$\begin{aligned} E_{33} &= 44.12 \text{ GPa}, \quad E_{11} = E_{22} = 12.41 \text{ GPa}, \\ G_{13} &= G_{23} = 4.46 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{12} = 4.14 \text{ GPa}, \\ \nu_{31} &= \nu_{32} = 0.29, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.5 \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

The interlaminar shear stress was evaluated at a 27° twist angle per 114.3 mm length, corresponding to the measured failure twist angle for this laminate [2]. Expressions (29) are used in the first approximation (18). To simplify the calculations, the functions $f_x^{(i)}(x)$ and $\psi_x^{(i)}(x)$ in eqns (18) and (19) do not change from ply to ply. The functions of y are independent for each ply. The above simplification allows integrating weak forms (22) and (23) over the total thickness of the cross section for the second iteration. The third iterations for one- and two-term approximations are compared with the finite element cross sectional analysis in Fig. 4. One-term approximation predicts the correct trend with a 9% discrepancy compared to the finite element result for the maximum stress value. The predictions of two-term approximation show a maximum discrepancy of less than 2%. One-term approximation requires solution of 54 linear algebraic equations at the first and the third iterations. Two-term approximation results in 108 linear algebraic equations at each odd iteration.

Fig. 4. Comparison of interlaminar shear stress predictions at the free edge $x = b$ for torsion of $[0_{12}/\pm 30_2]_s$ laminate

Fig. 5. Influence of damage on torsional stiffness of unidirectional orthotropic beam

And finally, comparison with a boundary element model for the torsional rigidity of a damaged S2/F584 glass-epoxy unidirectional orthotropic beam is discussed. The cross section thickness and width are 10 mm and 40 mm, respectively. The material properties are provided in eqns (35). An edge crack of length a is positioned horizontally at a quarter-thickness distance from the middle surface. In Fig. 5, the torsional rigidity

$$GJ = \frac{1}{\theta} \iint_{\substack{-b \leq x \leq b \\ -h \leq y \leq h}} (\sigma^{yz} x - \sigma^{xz} y) dx dy \quad (36)$$

normalized by the torsional rigidity of the undamaged beam, is plotted versus the delamination length, normalized by the cross section half-width. Comparison of one-term approximation for the stress function with the boundary element predictions is presented in that figure. The boundary element model is based on the collocation method [12]. The maximum discrepancy between the second iteration and the boundary element results is less than 4%. The analytical model required solution of 8 linear algebraic equations at each iteration while the maximum number of degrees of freedom in the boundary element model was 280.

CONCLUSION

An iterative method for the approximate analytical solution of elasticity problems for composite laminates is presented. Interlaminar stresses and stiffness parameters for laminates subjected to axial extension and torsion are evaluated. A good agreement with the existing cross sectional model predictions illustrates the validity of the method. For the examples considered in this study, one-term approximation predicts a correct trend information, and two-term approximation provides a good numerical accuracy for stresses. One-term approximation resulted in an accurate prediction of stiffness parameters. Only two or three iterations are sufficient for accurate modeling. An advantage of the method over existing numerical or analytical models is its simplicity, which makes the method appealing for parametric design studies.

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